

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 96

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 96

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 96:1 “Sing to the LORD a ^bnew song;</p> <p style="padding-left: 2em;">Sing to the LORD, all the earth.</p> <p>² Sing to the LORD, bless His name; “Proclaim good tidings of His salvation from day to day.</p> <p>³ Tell of “His glory among the nations, His wonderful deeds among all the peoples.</p> <p>⁴ For “great is the LORD and ^bgreatly to be praised; He is to be “feared ^dabove all gods.</p> <p>⁵ For “all the gods of the peoples are ¹idols, But ^bthe LORD made the heavens.</p> <p>⁶ “Splendor and majesty are before Him, Strength and beauty are in His sanctuary.</p> <p>Psa. 96:7 ¹Ascribe to the LORD, O “families of the peoples, ^{1b}Ascribe to the LORD glory and strength.</p> <p>⁸ ¹Ascribe to the LORD the “glory of His name; Bring an ^{2b}offering and come into His courts.</p> <p>⁹ “Worship the LORD in ¹holy attire; ^bTremble before Him, all the earth.</p> <p>¹⁰ Say among the nations, ““The LORD reigns; Indeed, the “world is firmly established, it will not be moved;</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">Psa. 96:1</p> <p>שִׁירוּ לַיהוָה שִׁיר חֲדָשׁ שִׁירוּ לַיהוָה כָּל־הָאָרֶץ : ² שִׁירוּ לַיהוָה בְּרָכוּ שְׁמוֹ בַשָּׁרׁוּ מִיּוֹם־ לַיּוֹם יִשׁוּעָתוֹ : ³ סַפְּרוּ בְּגוֹיִם כְּבוֹדוֹ בְּכָל־הָעַמִּים נִפְלְאוֹתָיו : ⁴ כִּי גָדוֹל יְהוָה וּמְהֻלָּל מְאֹד נִזְרָא הוּא עַל־כָּל־אֱלֹהִים : ⁵ כִּי אֶפְסֵי־ אֱלֹהֵי הָעַמִּים אֱלִילִים וַיְהִי שָׁמַיִם עָשָׂה : ⁶ הוֹדוּ־וְהִדְרִי לִפְנֵי עֲזוֹ וְתִפְאַרֶת בְּמִקְדָּשׁוֹ : ⁷ הִבּוּ לַיהוָה מִשִּׁפְתֹת עַמִּים הִבּוּ לַיהוָה כְּבוֹד וְעֹז : ⁸ הִבּוּ לַיהוָה כְּבוֹד שְׁמוֹ שְׂאוּ־מִנְחָה וּבְאוּ לְחַצְרוֹתָיו : ⁹ הַשִּׁתְחַוּוּ לַיהוָה בְּהַדְרַת־קֹדֶשׁ חִילוּ מִפְּנֵי כָל־הָאָרֶץ : ¹⁰ אִמְרוּ בְּגוֹיִם אֵי־יְהוָה מֶלֶךְ אֶרֶץ־תִּכּוֹן תִּבְלַ בַּל־תִּמּוֹט יָדִין עַמִּים בְּמִישְׁרִים : ¹¹ יִשְׁמְחוּ הַשָּׁמַיִם וְתִגַּל הָאָרֶץ יִרְעַם הַיָּם וּמְלֹאוֹ : ¹² יַעֲלוּ שָׁרֵי וְכָל־ אֲשֶׁר־בּוֹ אֲזוּ יִרְנְנוּ כָּל־עֲצֵי־יַעַר : ¹³ לִפְנֵי יְהוָה אֲפִי בָּא כִּי בָּא לְשִׁפְט הָאָרֶץ יִשְׁפֹט־תִּבְלַ בְּצַדִּיק וְעַמִּים בְּאַמוֹנָתוֹ :</p>

He will ^bjudge the peoples with ¹equity.”

Psa. 96:11 Let the ^aheavens be glad, and let the ^bearth rejoice;

Let ^cthe sea ¹roar, and ²all it contains;

¹² Let the ^afield exult, and all that is in it.

Then all the ^btrees of the forest will sing for joy

¹³ Before the LORD, ^afor He is coming,

For He is coming to judge the earth.

^bHe will judge the world in righteousness

And the peoples in His faithfulness.

References

Psalm 96:1

^a1 Chr 16:23-33

^bPs 40:3

Psalm 96:2

^aPs 71:15

Psalm 96:3

^aPs 145:12

Psalm 96:4

^aPs 48:1; 145:3

^bPs 18:3

^cPs 89:7

^dPs 95:3

Psalm 96:5

¹Or *non-existent things*

^a1 Chr 16:26; Jer 10:11

^bPs 115:15; Is 42:5

Psalm 96:6

^aPs 104:1

Psalm 96:7

¹Lit *Give*

^aPs 22:27

^b1 Chr 16:28, 29; Ps 29:1, 2

Psalm 96:8

¹Lit *Give*

²Or *meal offering*

^aPs 79:9; 115:1

^bPs 45:12; 72:10

Psalm 96:9

¹Or *the splendor of holiness*

^a1 Chr 16:29; 2 Chr 20:21; Ps 29:2; 110:3

^bPs 33:8; 114:7

Psalm 96:10

¹Or *uprightness*

^aPs 93:1; 97:1

^bPs 9:8; 58:11; 67:4; 98:9

Psalm 96:11

¹Or *thunder*

²Lit *its fullness*

^aPs 69:34; Is 49:13

^bPs 97:1

^cPs 98:7

Psalm 96:12

^aPs 65:13; Is 35:1; 55:12, 13

^bIs 44:23

Psalm 96:13

^aPs 98:9

^bRev 19:11

Targum

Psa. 96:1 Sing in the presence of the LORD a new psalm; sing praise, angels of the height, sing praise in the presence of the LORD, all righteous of the earth. ² Sing praise in the presence of the LORD, bless his name; proclaim his redemption from day to day. ³ Tell of his glory among the Gentiles, of his wonders among all the peoples. ⁴ For great is the LORD and greatly to be praised; and he is more to be feared than any god. ⁵ For all the things feared by the Gentiles are idols; but the LORD made the heavens. ⁶ Praise and splendor are in his presence; strength and praise are in his sanctuary. ⁷ Make music in the presence of the LORD, O races of peoples; ascribe glory and strength in the presence of the LORD. ⁸ Ascribe glory in the presence of the LORD, and exalt his name; carry and bring an offering and enter his presence in his courts. ⁹ Bow down before him in the splendor of holiness; tremble in his presence, all inhabitants of the earth. ¹⁰ Say among the Gentiles, “The LORD reigns”; also the world is made firm that it will not totter; he will judge the peoples uprightly. ¹¹ The forces of heaven will rejoice and the righteous of the earth will exult; the sea will shout and all its fullness. ¹² The field and everything in it will pour forth praise; then all the trees of the forest will sing – ¹³ In the presence of the LORD, for he comes, for he comes to judge the earth; he will judge the world with righteousness and the peoples with his faithfulness.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

This Psalm is the seventh Psalm composed by Moses. Ibn Yachya¹ attempted to identify the tribes of the five remaining Psalms of Moses. He believed this Psalm was dedicated to Zebulun, who rejoiced when he went out to earn a livelihood so his brother Issachar could study the Torah. Zebulun would constantly sing to the LORD a new song thanking Him for the Divine blessing which resulted from his wealth.

David adapted this Psalm to his circumstances. The sage Radak believed that David did this when the Ark of the Covenant returned from exile in Philista. When Israel is released from exile, the Jews will join the Messiah and exult: Sing to HaShem a new song to Hashem to everyone on earth.

Notes to the Psalm

Verses four and five show that the idea of monotheism had not yet spread across the earth. The God of Israel was the God who created Heaven and Earth. However, the LORD was not the God of all nations yet. Each nation had its own gods. These were false gods, and worshiping them was idolatry. The psalmist says that eventually, all nations of the world will come to know the LORD and that the LORD is the only God of Heaven and Earth because He created all things.

¹ 16th century Bible commentator, a member of the famous Ibn Yachia family which produced many great Torah scholars. He composed a commentary on the Five Megilot, and a book on Gan Eden and the afterlife called "Torah Ohr." Two other books, "Derech Ha-Chaim" and "Ner Mitzva" were lost during the burning of the Talmud in Padua in 1414. His son Gedaliah is the author of "Shalshes HaKabbalah". From: <https://www.sefaria.org/topics/joseph-ibn-yachya?tab=sources>

Atheists challenge monotheism today, especially those who say they belong to a monotheistic religion but worship idolatrous gods. This is a theme that has been found in several Psalms. The god of materialism is a false god. Its followers are more concerned about their wealth and power, shrugging off any consequences of their actions.

In Christianity, there is a ritual called the “deathbed conversion.” A sinner or one who committed idolatry with materialism on their deathbed prays that the LORD will forgive them. A pastor or priest arrives and baptizes the person. Everyone present is glad that the baptism ritual was performed. However, did it make a difference? Anyone on their deathbed can say that they believe in Jesus Christ as their savior at the very end.

Issachar reminds us that one must study the Torah and Prophets as a part of their life. This means to live by the Word of the LORD. The last-minute confessions are invalid in the eyes of the LORD. Each human will answer for sin. The Zohar says that the LORD gives people ample time to repent and to make restitution for all sins. If death comes before the sins are repented, that is the person’s fault. A last-minute effort to be “saved” will not happen.

Appendix

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

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